

DO WE WANT TO LIBERALIZE TRADE OR VICE VERSA

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Annotation: There are several specific ways to restrict sales. Trade restrictions can be conditionally divided into: duty-free, non-duty-free and covert methods (in some cases they are applied simultaneously). Well-known customs restrictions are the setting of customs duties on goods imported into this country, and non-duty methods are examples of quantitative restrictions (quotas) (I will not dwell on them now because the hidden methods are not relevant).

Key words: to restrict sales , imported goods, custom duty , quotas, the amount of tariffs, to support domestic producers , the government, the vivid example of quantitative restrictions

Introduction: The main difference between quantitative restrictions and duties is that annual (monthly or quarterly) quantitative restrictions are imposed on goods imported into the country (for example, the country can import 100 tons of sugar this year). Once the amount of imports reaches a certain level, the import of this product will be completely stopped (for example, if the import of sugar reaches 100 tons, it will be impossible to import other sugar into the country). But now quotas alone are rarely applied. That is, they often come with duties. For example (imaginary example), there is a 10% import duty for 100 tons of sugar imports. Every kilogram of sugar imported over 100 tons is subject to, say, 100% duty. There are many similar examples, such as South Korea or Japan using quota tariffs in order to retain domestic rice producers. They import about 400,000 tons (about 25% of total consumption) of rice imports (in Korea) at 5% tariffs, and this amount is distributed to several partner countries. Once the volume of imports reaches 400,000 tons, each kg of imported rice is subject to customs duties of more than 500% (which makes importing almost impossible).

According to the regulation adopted on December 2, tariff quotas will be introduced on imported goods. I have a few questions and concerns. First, the statute seemed very vague to me, i.e., if the statute imposes lower-than-established duties for a specified quantity of imported goods, the applicable

duties apply for an amount exceeding the specified amount (I tried to make it as easy as possible from the appearance in the statute). At first glance, it seems that our trade is liberalizing, that is, for some quantities lower than the current, and for imports in excess of that amount, the current tariffs are in fact trade liberalization, but then what does this rule have to do with the decision to support domestic producers. That is, if we are adopting this regulation to support domestic producers, then the above view of the regulation would be more illogical. In my opinion, for the amount exceeding the established quota, the new established customs regime will be applied, not the current one. Secondly, this regulation is very dangerous in two respects. According to the regulations, one ministry (Investment and Foreign Trade) allocates a certain quota to importers. In other words, the government decides for itself who to grant the right to import. This in itself leads to an increase in corruption not only in our country but in any other country (i.e. for some reason the government gives more quotas to importer A than to importer B and does not explain the reason to anyone).

In other words, the current form of quota not only monopolizes the domestic market, but also monopolizes imports as a result of the transfer of the right to import to the government. In addition, the state also determines from which countries to import, which can also be detrimental to consumers. For example, a government may find that giving a quota to one state, while more expensive than some political ambitions, is preferable to a state that is actually cheaper than another. In the third place, domestic producers can submit their proposals to the above-mentioned ministries. This could lead to the imposition of import quotas on the goods they produce by putting pressure on ministries by some manufacturers with significant influence in the domestic market or by illegally influencing them. This in itself could lead to further long-term liberalization of trade for some industries that have long been hurting consumers.

In conclusion, even if tariff quotas do not exceed import barriers, a sharp increase in government intervention in the market could have dire consequences for consumers. I think the government may be trying to limit trade through such a method in order to continue to protect domestic producers that it has been protecting for so long on the eve of joining some international organization. In any case, it is very likely that this regulation will serve to increase rather than increase consumer welfare

The government, which really wants to liberalize trade, is trying to liberalize and simplify it, rather than restricting and complicating it in various new ways. Unfortunately, I do not see such a trend in us yet

List of used literature:

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